

Rethinking Residual Emissions of Local Authorities in England: Utilising Green Assets

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March 2025

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*<https://www.elsevier.com/en-gb/researcher/author/policies-and-guidelines/credit-author-statement>

Cite as: Kuppaswamy C., and Asif, H. (2025) *Rethinking Residual Emissions of Local Authorities in England: Utilising Green Assets*. Hatfield, UK: Centre for Climate Change Research, University of Hertfordshire. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14999471

**SUBNATIONAL GREENHOUSE
GAS EMISSIONS FROM THE
PUBLIC SECTOR ACCOUNTS FOR
2.7% OF TOTAL EMISSIONS**

Source: Total primary emissions of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O UK
local and regional greenhouse gas emissions estimates for
2005-2020 Technical report, pg.11

LAs as Incidental emitters

The UK, as a historical emitter, bears a greater responsibility for mitigating emissions under the principle of "common but differentiated responsibilities" in international law. Similarly, within the UK, emissions responsibility varies, with Local Authorities (LAs) being incidental emitters due to their historically low contributions. This disparity forms the rationale for reevaluating LA residual emissions in this report.

Source: Vigna, L., Friedrich, J., and Damassa, T., The History of Carbon Dioxide Emissions (3 June 2024) World Resources Institute, <https://www.wri.org/insights/history-carbon-dioxide-emissions> accessed 10 November 2024

LAs as influencers in reducing territorial emissions

Local Authorities (LAs) are pivotal in driving regional emissions reduction, whether through declared Climate Emergencies or their mandate under the Local Government Act to promote local well-being. Their role extends beyond managing their own operational emissions; they must actively influence core emitters within their jurisdiction. Recognising LAs as incidental emitters, distinct from major sectors like transport or domestic users, necessitates a revised approach to residual emissions (REs). Given their broader responsibility, the sustainability community should view LA resources as strategically located to enhance their capacity as influential actors, rather than solely focusing on their own operational reductions.

Source: Local Government Act 2000, UK Public General Acts 2000 c. 22 Explanatory Notes Introduction Part I: Promotion of Economic, Social Or Environmental Well-Being Background <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2000/22/notes/division/1/1/2> accessed 14 Nov 2024

Source: Louise Marix Evans (Dec 2020) *Local Authorities and the Sixth Carbon Budget*. An independent report for the Climate Change Committee. <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/local-authorities-and-the-sixth-carbon-budget/> accessed 12 June 2024

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Paris Agreement has broadened emissions reduction duties and enlisted a much larger number of economies into the fight against rising GHG emissions. Whilst this is in principle beneficial for addressing climate change, it has resulted in settled concepts being applied to all carbon markets. Local authorities (“LAs”) are being held to similar standards as the private sector despite their different responsibilities in addressing climate change. This research critically examines the concept of additionality – a fundamental principle in carbon markets - and identifies blurriness in how the concept is understood. In pinning down the concept as legal additionality, the research assesses whether local authorities in the UK have legal duties towards a variety of carbon sinks, collectively referred to in this report as “green assets”. With the exception of wetlands, which are legally protected, other green assets assessed, i.e. managed trees, ancient woodlands, soil, and grass verges exist at the discretion of their landowners, i.e. local authorities, and are not mandated by law. By maintaining them, local authorities can derive carbon accounting benefit from them by counting them as high-quality carbon offsets to offset local authority residual emissions.

To stimulate a wider policy discussion on green assets and their role in local authorities’ carbon offset strategy, this report recommends the following: -

- 1. Stratify additionality**
 - a. Establish different degrees of additionality tailored to the public sector**
 - b. Differentiate the value of offsets based on asset types and management practices**
- 2. Quantify and certify Green Asset Offsets**
 - a. Review and agree upon the carbon sequestration potential capacity of managed trees, woodlands, soil, grass verges and pitches.**
 - b. Align standards with recognised certification schemes**
- 3. Develop a clear carbon offset strategy**
 - a. Define principles appropriate for the public sector**
 - b. Enhance transparency to avoid greenwashing concerns.**
- 4. Consider the climate finance potential of increasing green assets**
 - a. Explore funding mechanisms to increase green asset portfolio**

1. UK Territorial Emissions and the contribution of the Public Sector

UK territorial emissions refers to emissions produced solely within the UK's territory. This metric is used when tracking progress towards national and international climate change targets like net zero emissions by 2050. The sectorwise breakdown of emissions below shows that the public sector was responsible for 10,785 kt CO₂, i.e. 2.7% of total emissions. The public sector encompasses local authorities ("LAs") as LAs fall within the scope of 'Public sector' as defined in the UK Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes.¹

UK local and regional greenhouse gas emissions estimates for 2005-2020: Technical Report

Table 2 UK Total End user emissions of CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O (kt CO₂ 2020)

Sector	Anthracite & Coal	Coke	SSF & Charcoal	Natural Gas	Oil	Electricity	Non-Fuel	Grand Total
Energy Supply								
Energy Consumption								
Industry: Iron & Steel	166	10,704	-	909	80	328	752	12,939
Industry: Other Combustion	1,896	-	-	20,487	12,614	14,455	256	49,707
Industry: Other Processes	1,428	-	-	2,031	5,732	-	7,347	16,538
Commercial	31	-	-	11,404	170	11,357	724	23,687
Agriculture	-	-	-	207	4,547	814	39,471	45,039
Miscellaneous	-	-	-	-	-	-	17,653	17,653
Rail Transport	38	-	-	2	1,522	902	-	2,464
Domestic	1,500	-	837	58,384	8,685	21,444	293	91,143
Public	59	-	-	7,793	100	2,834	-	10,785
Road Transport	-	-	-	62	103,450	112	57	103,681
Inland Waterways	-	-	-	-	928	-	-	928
Land use Change	-	-	-	-	-	-	4,607	4,607
Water Transport: National Navigation	-	-	-	-	4,783	-	-	4,783
Air Transport	-	-	-	-	603	-	-	603
Military Transport (Air & Water)	-	-	-	-	1,542	-	-	1,542
Exports	-	-	11	-	4,480	906	-	5,397
International aviation and shipping	-	-	-	-	1,771	-	-	1,771
Total	5,118	10,704	848	101,280	151,008	53,151	71,159	393,269

Legend and Notes:

Energy Suppliers
Energy Users
Others (CO ₂ emissions not related to fuel use)

Sectors: Excluded from Local GHG estimates in *italic*

Despite their relatively low direct emissions, the public sector is the only sector in this table² with the remit to influence other sectors through policies. Other sectors such as transport, residential and commercial can only have secondary influence through their business strategies if government policies have created an enabling environment to reduce emissions.

¹ Specifically in subsections 84-87 of UK Standard Industrial Classification of Economic Activities 2007 – SIC (2007), used by the UK technical report on local and regional GHG emissions estimates for 2005 to 2020. LAs fall within the scope of section 84 of SIC 2007, which includes administration of the State and the economic and social policy of the community.

² This table is neither the latest estimate (2005-2022 is currently available) nor inclusive of emissions breakdown at county level (which is also available). However, this table has been included, as in the latest estimates (up to 2022) the emissions data is presented differently, and the 2020 version is relevant to this paper. This table puts in context public sector/local authority emissions and shows that the share of local authority emissions is minimal in comparison to the other sectors of the UK. It also draws attention to the contribution of sectors such as domestic and commercial sectors over which LAs have influence over, and which are much larger contributors to emissions than the public sector.

2. Residual Emission of Local Authorities

In Hertfordshire, most LAs have declared climate emergencies and are progressing action plans for emissions reduction. Nevertheless, there is a recognition that despite significant decarbonisation efforts, some emissions will remain unavoidable, and therefore LAs will need to offset their emissions to meet any carbon declarations. Traditionally, those LAs that have progressed purchased offsets have relied on paying for carbon credits on the open market.

This paper considers whether Local Authorities could recognise green assets from within their own estates that may lead to carbon sequestration. The carbon sequestration capacity of local authorities 'green assets' can be considered even while baselining the emissions of the local authorities (similar to IMCOs or International Mitigation Compensation Outcomes).

Green Assets

In this report, green assets under LA management include

1. Managed Trees
2. Ancient Woodlands
3. Verges/Hedges and football pitches
4. Soil
5. Wetlands

The report considers the legal duties and obligations related to the planting, maintenance, and care of green assets by LAs. Why do local authorities maintain them, and how can the benefit help them towards their aspiration of addressing climate change?

The significance of LA green assets is understudied, and this report aims to fill this gap. Local authorities maintain and plant trees, keep soil exposed on their land, maintain and protect wetlands for various reasons including health, well-being, biodiversity, and for aesthetic purposes. These green assets inherently sequester carbon at varying levels and therefore mitigate emissions yet their potential as offsets remains underexplored.

Often at the discretion of local authorities, green assets are not legal duties and are therefore subject to the risk of being removed or neglected. Further detail on the legal duties relating to green assets is provided in a later section in this paper. However, if green assets are incorporated into formal offsetting strategies, LAs could balance residual emissions while providing co benefits for health, wellbeing and the landscape.

Defining a High-Quality Carbon Offset

At the heart of the issue is the question of what constitutes a "high-quality" carbon offset. In the absence of a formal regulatory framework, local authorities *must* establish their own criteria. In order to establish a LA framework for a high-quality offset, this paper considers how LAs might define what standards or principles to be led by.

The principles that are used to constitute good practice for local authorities are ordinarily considered to be the Nolan Principles (1995), Local Government Act (2000), Localism Act (2011), the Green Book (2020) and potentially best practice on local government procurement also.

Collating these principles and applying them to an offsetting context would suggest that the most pertinent themes to be considered for a robust offsetting scheme could be ensuring that a project has:

- Robust transparent evidence.
- Co-benefits for the local community.
- Financial quality in the form of longevity and fair value, to demonstrate a sound financial investment of public funds.

These guidelines need to be based on scientific and statutory evidence and must meet stringent standards of rigour. The key characteristics of a high-quality carbon offset (Oxford Offsetting Principles 2024 and Three Rivers Commissioned Research 2024) are generally as follows:

1. Compensate for hard-to-treat emissions.
2. Verifiable and certifiable (where possible)
3. Benefit the local natural habitat, community, and economy
4. Science-based accounting
5. Transparent disclosure
6. Focused on CO₂ removal
7. Focused on long-term CO₂ storage
8. High degree of additionality
9. Not create unintended environmental consequences.
10. Locally generated or sourced
11. Aligned to Biodiversity Net Gain activities.
12. Appropriate and sensitive to the existing habitat.

LA owned green assets can satisfy all the twelve criteria except one (criteria 8), which needs further investigation:

Depending on the strength of the LA's carbon reduction plans, it is completely possible to satisfy criteria 1. The LA should go for deep decarbonization before opting for offsetting through green assets, if this is the case, then green assets will only be used to compensate for hard-to-treat emissions.

It is possible to get certifications from the Woodland Trust for those green assets that satisfy the Woodland Carbon Code, in other cases it is possible to set up verification mechanisms, thus satisfying criteria 2.

Green assets benefit the local natural habitat, community, and the economy (criteria 3).

By following the Woodland Code or similar, the accounting for carbon removal by green assets will be science-based, and transparent, if published, meeting criteria 4 and 5.

Green assets act by removing carbon from the atmosphere as opposed to reducing the addition of carbon to the atmosphere, which offsets such as renewable energy projects do, meeting criteria 6.

Depending on the type of green asset, it is possible to go for long term CO₂ storage via green assets (criteria 7).

Green assets create next to nil unintended environmental consequences and are locally based (criteria 9 and 10).

They are very much the same as biodiversity net gain activities, and appropriate and sensitive to the existing habitat (criteria 11 and 12).

Criterion 8, the requirement of a high degree of additionality is not easy to answer and requires further investigation.

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Axelsson, K., Wagner, A., Johnstone, I., Allen, M., Caldecott, B., Eyre, N., Fankhauser, S., Hale, T., Hepburn, C., Hickey, C., Khosla, R., Lezak, S., Mitchell-Larson, E., Malhi, Y., Seddon, N., Smith, A. and Smith, S.M. 2024. *Oxford Principles for Net Zero Aligned Carbon Offsetting* (revised 2024). Oxford: Smith School of Enterprise and the Environment, University of Oxford.

Additionality

The concept of additionality is described in various sources:

- *The Gold Standard*: This widely recognized carbon offset standard defines additionality as "the determination that a project activity leads to GHG emission reductions or removals that are additional to what would have occurred in the absence of the certified project activity." (The Gold Standard. (n.d.). *Gold Standard for the Global Goals*. <https://www.goldstandard.org/>)
- *Verified Carbon Standard (VCS)*: The VCS, another leading standard, states that "additionality is a fundamental requirement for all VCS projects and is assessed based on a project's specific context and circumstances." (*Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) Program*. <https://verra.org/project/vcs-program/>)
- *The World Bank*: The World Bank's Carbon Finance Unit describes additionality as "the demonstration that an intervention has caused GHG emission reductions or removals that would not have occurred without the intervention."

- *Academic Literature:* Additionality is a cornerstone of carbon offsetting, ensuring that projects genuinely contribute to climate mitigation by delivering emission reductions or removals that would not have occurred otherwise (Gillenwater, 2012).

The notion of additionality originated in the context of the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) under the Kyoto Protocol (Michaelowa & Fages, 1999). It aimed to prevent carbon credits from being awarded to projects that would have happened anyway, ensuring that offsetting genuinely contributes to climate action. Over time, additionality has become a central tenet in the voluntary carbon market (VCM), with various standards and methodologies incorporating it as a core requirement.

A notable incident where the principle of additionality was questioned within the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) involved HFC-23 destruction projects. HFC-23 is a potent greenhouse gas produced as a byproduct in the manufacturing of HCFC-22, a refrigerant gas. In the early years of the CDM, projects focused on destroying HFC-23 were highly profitable due to the large number of carbon credits they generated. However, it was discovered that some companies were intentionally increasing HFC-23 production solely to benefit from the CDM incentives. This practice undermined the principle of additionality because the HFC-23 destruction was not truly "additional" to what would have happened anyway.

This incident raised concerns about the environmental integrity of the CDM and led to stricter additionality rules being implemented. In 2011, the European Union (EU) banned the use of HFC-23 credits in its Emissions Trading System (ETS) due to concerns about their lack of additionality.

This case study highlights the importance of rigorous additionality assessment in carbon offsetting projects to ensure that they genuinely contribute to climate mitigation and avoid incentivising perverse behaviour.

Historical Origins of Additionality (Before the Paris Agreement)

The concept of offsetting originated from early emissions trading mechanisms, particularly under the 1977 Clean Air Act in the United States. Initially, this approach assessed whether permitted facilities could increase emissions only if another company offset those emissions through greater reductions elsewhere. This practice established the foundational ideas of assessing additionality and baselines in relation to regulatory standards (Gillenwater, 2012).

The assessment of additionality within climate change policy began with a pilot program initiated after the first Conference of Parties (COP-1) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in 1995. This program, known as Activities Implemented Jointly (AIJ), allowed developed countries to undertake emission reduction projects in developing countries and receive credit for those reductions. A debate on additionality emerged due to concerns that funding for AIJ projects might be sourced from existing international aid budgets. Developing countries sought to ensure that this funding was truly new and not merely a relabeling of existing development assistance. The Berlin Mandate at COP-1 defined additionality as environmental benefits that would not have occurred without the project, explicitly stating that project financing should be in addition to existing financial obligations and official development assistance (ODA).

The Kyoto Protocol, adopted in December 1997 in Kyoto, Japan, by all developed nations except the United States, aimed to reduce global carbon emissions. Article 12.5(c) of the Kyoto Protocol defines the additionality of Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) projects as reductions in emissions that are additional to any that would occur in the absence of the certified project activity. Furthermore, Article 6.1(b) of the Protocol describes additionality in the context of Joint Implementation (JI) projects as a reduction in emissions by sources, or an enhancement of removals by sinks, that is additional to any that would otherwise occur. However, Gillenwater (2012) argues that the Kyoto Protocol's description of its CDM and JI mechanisms provided little clarity on the concept of additionality beyond what was established in the Berlin Mandate. He notes that the definition of additionality for CDM projects hinges heavily on the word "certified," yet the Protocol offers no guidance on what constitutes additionality, as there is no outlined certification process. Moreover, the Protocol fails to provide guidelines or criteria for identifying policy interventions.

To address the ambiguity surrounding additionality in the Kyoto Protocol, the Meth Panel was formed in 2002. Their first draft for CDM project proposals required proponents to confirm that the project wouldn't exist without the CDM, essentially establishing the carbon offset program itself as the benchmark for determining additionality. However, this approach was revised due to stakeholder pushback. The second draft emphasised the need to consider policies but lacked clarity on their role in defining the baseline. Further attempts to clarify the concept were made, but the guidance remained vague, resulting in subjective assessments of additionality in the first CDM projects (Asuka and Takeuchi, 2004).

Despite recognising the need for more clarity on the CDM and JI mechanisms before their implementation, the UNFCCC parties failed to reach a consensus on a precise definition of additionality during COP-7 (Michaelowa, 2009).

The resulting Marrakesh Accords (2001) defined project additionality in relation to reduced emissions compared to a baseline scenario; a concept largely unchanged from the original Kyoto language. Michaelowa (2009) suggests that negotiators' inability to define additionality stemmed from several factors: disagreements between involved parties, insufficient comprehension of the issues (especially by developing countries), and the perception that it was a technical matter rather than a negotiation point.

Initially, CDM determined additionality from the project perspective against a baseline. In 2004, the CDM Board introduced an additionality tool consisting of various tests, including investment, regulatory, barrier, and common practice, or a hybrid of these. However, after 2011, CDM additionality testing was simplified and standardised. Joint Implementation (JI), another offsetting mechanism under the Kyoto Protocol, allowed countries with emission reduction commitments to issue Emission Reduction Units (ERU) from greenhouse gas reduction projects and transfer these to other countries. Under Track 1, it was up to the individual country to determine if the project was additional, i.e. if the country would genuinely reduce emissions. However, this system appeared flawed for countries with less stringent emission goals. Under Track 2 stricter additionality rules were implemented in accordance with criteria like those used in the CDM (Michaelowa et al., 2019).

Meanwhile in 2005, the United States introduced its first market-based program Regional Green House Initiatives (RGGI) to cap the ghg emissions and the EU introduced the Emissions trading system (ETS). By 2009, all three carbon regulation schemes in effect—the Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative (RGGI) in the United States, the EU Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS), and the Kyoto Protocol—all required additionality of offsets, which made additionality more of a regulatory concept. All three programs exclude the preservation of existing forest resources from credit. (Ferrey, 2009).

Gillenwater (2012) concludes that additionality concerns what is caused by a policy intervention, and the assessment of additionality involves predicting what would happen without the policy intervention and then comparing a proposal to that prediction. Despite extensive discussions and debates over two decades, there remains no consensus in the climate change and development sectors regarding the precise definition of additionality and its most effective implementation methods (Michaelowa et al., 2019).

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VOLUNTARY CARBON MARKET

Additionality has derived its meaning from the voluntary carbon market context, via the Kyoto Protocol, which regulates private enterprise involved in products and services that result in GHG emissions. It was not directed at the public sector who have different responsibilities to the private sector.

Determining Additionality:

Table 2. Concepts and Determination Methods for Additionality

Methods	Barrier testing	Investment analysis	Common practice, technological analysis	Checklists
Emissions additionality	Under emissions additionality, all three tests can be used in shaping the range of available baseline scenarios and determining the baseline.			Checklists will likely reflect a previous analysis built on the other three types of tests (barrier, Investment and common practice analysis).
Technological additionality	Barrier tests will be focused on technological barriers, but it is not directly suited to technological additionality.	Technological additionality does not depend only on financial costs but other factors affecting the availability of the technology.	Common practice tests follow implicitly the logic of technological additionality.	Eligibility criteria/ positive lists will be based on the type of technology proposed, usually with some conditions on technology uptake.
Financial additionality	Barrier testing will be focused on barriers to investment, such as poor credit conditions.	Investment analysis is the essential type of test if focused on deriving the financial additionality of a given investment.	Technological analysis would not matter so much for financial additionality, unless a direct link is presumed or can be ascertained between the profitability of a technology and its uptake (ignoring other social and policy factors).	Eligibility criteria will be based on financial indicators.

Reference: Carbon Credits and Additionality, Technical note, 2016, World Bank Group

Additionality Tests

Additionality tests in carbon markets ensure that emissions reductions are beyond what would have occurred without the intervention. Traditional approaches adopted by existing crediting mechanisms include:

- **A regulatory surplus test** that asks whether the project activity is required by law, mandate, court order, or regulation. Required activities are deemed non-additional. Exceptions may be made when a policy or regulation is generally not widely followed or enforced.
- **A financial or investment test** that analyses whether the project activity is economically and financially viable. If the proposed project in question is economically viable without the carbon credit revenue, it would be deemed non-additional. This test is often operationalised in the form of an estimated internal rate of return for the proposed project relative to a contextually relevant investment benchmark. Another option is to compare the net present value of the project to a reference level. The project is considered non-additional if either the internal rate of return is above the benchmark or the net present value of the project is higher than the reference level.

• **A barrier test**, whereby project proponents need to identify obstacles to implementation. Additionality is demonstrated if the incentive from the crediting mechanism helps the project proponent overcome defined financial, technological, institutional, or regulatory barriers, which otherwise are preventing the project activity.

• **A common practice test or technology/practice penetration level test** that considers the proposed project’s technology or practice within its context (e.g., sector, region, and industry). If the technology or practice is established common practice and would likely occur even without the crediting mechanism, then the project or program is deemed to be non-additional.

Rules on Additionality in Different Carbon offset Programs:

Program Name	Rules on Additionality Determination
Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually determined on a project-by-project basis • Some small-scale positive lists have been developed, and technologies on a positive list are automatically considered additional. • A CDM project activity is additional if anthropogenic emissions of GHG by sources are reduced below those that would have occurred in the absence of the registered CDM project activity. • Rules on demonstrating additionality defined in the Additionality Tool (Step 1: Identification of alternatives to the project activity; Step 2: Investment analysis to determine that the proposed project activity is either (a) not the most economically or financially attractive or (b) not economically or financially feasible; Step 3: Barrier analysis; Step 4: Common practice analysis).
Joint Implementation (JI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Under track 1, requirements are set by the host Party and determined on a project-by-project basis. • [...] a host Party may verify reductions in anthropogenic emissions by sources or enhancements of anthropogenic removals by sinks from an Article 6 project as being additional to any that would otherwise occur [...] • In practice, verification of additionality varies significantly by the host party and JI track 2 rules are often applied, which allow for the use of the CDM Additionality Tool.
Gold Standard (GS)	<p>GS relies on the UNFCCC’s decision on additionality for CDM or JI projects applying for GS registration, and GS CDM or JI projects are not required to carry out a demonstration of additionality. • GS VER projects apply UNFCCC additionality requirements, including small-scale projects, validated by the DOEs (Designated Operational Entities) and further checked by the GS Secretariat. • Positive list approach for GS microscale projects.</p>
Verified Carbon Standard (VCS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All projects approved under the VCS must be additional, and the additionality requirements are those set out in the methodology that the project uses (for example, the CDM Additionality Tool).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New methodologies can include new approaches for the demonstration of additionality, either within the methodology or as a separate tool; both are subject to the VCS Methodology Approval Process. • A number of methodologies under development are applying a positive list for additionality, in line with the VCS framework for standardised methods
Japan’s Joint Crediting Mechanism (JCM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additionality determination is substituted by eligibility criteria for each of the methodologies, similar to a positive list. • Both governments (Japan and the host country) determine what technologies, products, and so on, should be included in the eligibility criteria through the approval process of the JCM methodologies by the Joint Committee. • Eligibility criteria for registration can be based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the efficiency of products/technologies (for example, tons output/kWh), a benchmark approach, or; • type of product/technology (that is, the group of accumulating methodologies will eventually form a kind of positive list). • Only projects that started their operation on or after January 1, 2013, are eligible.
California’s Compliance Offset Program (CA COP)	<p>GHG emissions reductions and GHG removal enhancements must be beyond what would otherwise be required by law, regulation, or legally binding mandate, and exceed what would otherwise occur in a conservative business-as-usual scenario.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offset credits can only be generated in sectors not covered by the CA Cap-and-Trade Program.
Quebec	<p>The reductions in GHG emissions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • must result from a project that is voluntary, that is not being carried out at the time or registration of renewal, in response to a legislative or regulatory provision, a permit or other type of authorisation, an order made under an Act or regulation, or a court decision; • must result from a project that goes beyond the current practices described in the applicable protocol for the project.
Climate Action Reserve (CAR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHG reductions must be additional to any that would have occurred in the absence of the Climate Action Reserve, or of a market for GHG reduction. • “Business as usual” reductions—that is, those that would occur in the absence of a GHG reduction market—should not be eligible for registration. • CAR additionality criteria include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a legal requirement test • a performance standard test (Section 2.4 of the Program Manual).
Australia’s Carbon Farming Initiative (AU CFI)	<p>Additionality test requires:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the project must go beyond common practice • must not be required by another law.

Switzerland's Program (CH OP)	Offset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usually determined on a project-by-project basis • Rules on demonstrating additionality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step 1: Identification of alternatives to the project activity • Step 2: Investment analysis to determine that the proposed project activity is either: (a) not the most economically or financially attractive or, (b) not economically or financially feasible • Step 3: Barrier analysis • Step 4: Common practice analysis • In programs, additionality can be determined for single activities on the basis of additionality criteria, similarly to the approach in the programmatic CDM.
Costa Rica		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The determination of additionality for a given class of project activity will be standardised. • The additionality is to be determined for the class of project activity, and qualifying conditions and criteria are to be set out in the methodology. • Individual projects need to meet the conditions and apply the predefined criteria set out in the standardised method, obviating the need for each project to determine additionality and/or the crediting baseline via project-specific approaches and analyses.
Thailand Emission Reduction Program (T-VER)	Voluntary Reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eligibility criteria for project activities will include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope/boundary: project activities located within the municipality geographical boundaries. • Baseline and monitoring: projects will apply methodologies under the T-VER. • Time: project activities starting after a given date. • Lawfulness: baseline cannot be illegal and project line must comply with environmental and legal requirements. • Double counting: project activity cannot benefit from another carbon standard. • Additionality: project activity must comply with the additionality criteria set up by the T-VER.

Additionality in the Paris Agreement Era

The global climate governance had a breakthrough at United Nations Climate Change Conference COP21 in year 2015 in the form of Paris Agreement (PA). This agreement introduces nationally determined contributions (NDCs) of all parties which are voluntary mitigation targets set by each country, as well as a long-term low emission development strategy (LT-LEDS). Parties are required to submit their national emissions inventory report (Article 13.7) of anthropogenic emissions using good practice methodologies accepted by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) along with relevant information to track the progress of NDCs (UNFCCC 2015).

In contrast to that the Kyoto Protocol which highlights additionality both in Article 6.1b (Joint Implementation) and Article 12.5c (Clean Development Mechanism), the Paris Agreement doesn't explicitly mention additionality at all (Hermwille and Obergassel, 2018). Article 6 of the Paris Agreement enables Parties to engage in voluntary cooperation as they implement their nationally determined contributions (NDCs) in the form of two market-based approaches, one where they can issue international transfer of mitigation outcomes (ITMOs) as in article 6.2 which accommodates decentralised cooperation between parties with no comparable oversight in place. Second, a centralised mechanism to contribute to the mitigation of GHG is established by article 6.4 under authority and guidance of conference of the parties. Though article 6.2 enables customisation and innovation suited to the national strategies, the lack of oversight and standardisation may lead to reduced integrity and therefore the PA requires them to ensure environmental integrity, robust accounting, avoidance of double counting and promotion of sustainable development subject to a technical expert review.

The significant difference in the pre and post Paris Agreement period is that the duties of states have changed. In the pre-Paris era, the duty to mitigate emissions only lie with Annex I countries which are industrialised countries. Annex I countries are industrialized countries and economies in transition that are part of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). Examples of Annex I countries are Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, European Union, Finland, France, Germany, and Iceland, and the UK. Responsibilities of Annex I countries include reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, protection and development of sinks, reporting on measures taken to prevent climate change, and reporting data on greenhouse gas emissions. All of these responsibilities have now shifted to include non-Annex I countries. All countries that are now party to the Paris Agreement, which as of date is 195 countries have the same responsibility to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, protect sinks, report on measures to reduce emissions and provide data on greenhouse gas emissions. All countries are moving towards an all-sectors reduction of greenhouse gas emissions including energy, transport, agriculture, and other key emitting sectors. This changes the scenario with regards to national strategies on Article 6. Developing countries will need to strategise the pros and cons of selling ITMOs (international transfer of mitigation outcomes) versus using them for offsetting their own emissions which will be hard to reduce. Therefore, the availability of ITMOs is likely to reduce and shrink as all countries ramp up efforts to meet their net zero targets. ITMOs are likely to become IMCOs (International Mitigation Compensation Outcomes) or be used within countries to offset their own GHG emissions. With rules that aspire for enhanced environmental integrity, the challenge to produce larger number of ITMOs will become even more difficult to meet.

Given that article 4 and 6 of the agreement clearly stipulate promoting environmental integrity and avoidance of double counting, Hermwille and Obergassel (2018) believe that the concept of additionality remains crucial for upholding environmental integrity in market-based climate

actions under Article 6 of Paris Agreement. Ahonen et al. (2021) refers to environmental integrity to the principles to ensure that such collaborations actively contribute to reducing global GHG emissions or at a minimum should not result in an overall increase in emissions.

Although the rules and procedures for the new mechanism established by Article 6.4 of the Paris agreement specifically mention that each activity will be required to demonstrate additionality by using “a robust assessment that shows the activity would not have occurred in the absence of the incentives from the mechanism, taking into account all relevant national policies, including legislation, and representing mitigation that exceeds any mitigation that is required by law or regulation, and taking a conservative approach that avoids locking in levels of emissions, technologies or carbon-intensive practices...” In contrast, the only direct reference to additionality within the guidance underpinning Article 6.2 is to state that ITMOs must be “real, verified and additional (Gold Standard Report on Additionality, 2022).

Ahonen et al. 2021 suggests that even Article 6.2 guidance doesn't prescribe how additionality may be ensured by the countries in ITMOs, it's in every one's best interest to ensure that ITMOs represent actual additional outcomes and critical for the credibility of cooperative approaches and reputation of parties engaged in those approaches. Moreover, even in the Paris agreement, there is no guarantee that these NDCs will create “hot air” and hence will require additionality testing particularly under article 6.2 from the perspective of host countries in approving and authorising ITMO transfers.

Michealowa et al. (2019) recommends that if the host country agrees to an independent assessment of its NDC and this assessment finds that the NDC does not contain ‘hot air’, then activity-level additionality testing can be waived. Since very few countries have announced their NDCs so far, the Gold Standard argues that this waiver can be applied in a limited way. Moreover, an ambitious NDC target doesn't assure that this emission reduction target will be achieved by the host country.

According to the Gold Standard report on additionality (2022), the Paris agreement era demands a more stringent approach to additionality, moving beyond checking if the project is financially viable without carbon credits to assessing if the project is the most effective way to utilize those limited resources. On the other hand, Hermwille & Obergessel (2018) argue that even though a project activity clearly demonstrates additionality by leading to a real emission reduction, it may still not be enough when considering the country's fair share of global emission reduction. This will be a critical challenge for international governance.

Following COP29 in November 2024, some progress has been made in rules relating to additionality. But what needs more attention is that fact that the need for Article 6 to work effectively has been further enhanced given the failure of COP 29 outcomes to reach the finance goals that some countries were aspiring to. The agreed-upon NCQG (New Collective Quantifiable Goal) of \$300 billion per year target by 2035 is widely seen as significantly inadequate compared to the estimated needs of developing countries. Article 6 is the main mechanism left to unlock climate finance for developing countries. Article 6 is the predominant mechanism that links markets to climate action. Voluntary carbon markets are important to plug some of the gaps left by the increasing need for climate finance.

The post Paris Agreement era is putting more pressure on all countries to reduce emissions, and therefore increasing the importance contribution of the public sector by influencing the economy through policies and administrative measures. Decarbonisation of all sectors of the economy in developed countries as well as developing countries need to be scaled up within the constraints of shrinking availability of ITMOs for offsetting. Local authorities in the UK should

also be looking to explore other options than buying carbon credits via the voluntary carbon market sector or through ITMOs authorised by the host states of carbon removal projects.

Additionality in the UK Context: Land Use

An increasing number of private companies in the UK, and other landowners are considering using their land for developing carbon sequestration projects. These companies own land and have invested in a woodland creation project to generate their own supply of carbon units to use against their emissions in future. 'Growing their own' carbon units by creating woodland to compensate for greenhouse gas emissions elsewhere on their land holding or business. Getting their project validated and verified to the Woodland Carbon Code quantifies the benefit of this woodland creation and provides carbon units to compensate for the estate/business's wider emissions as they grow.

Status	Project Developer	Number of Units	Project Name
Verified	Galbraith (Owned by Caledonian Properties Ltd)	~11,000	<u>Caledonian Woodland Carbon Scheme</u> (case study)
Validated	Grosvenor	~37,000	<u>New carbon Woodlands 1</u> (UK Land Carbon Registry)
Verified	Thorlux Lighting	~30,000	<u>Cwm Fagor</u> (case study) <u>Cwm Fagor</u> (Verified - on UK Land Carbon Registry) <u>Cwm Fagor 2016-2017</u> (Validated - on UK Land Carbon Registry)
Verified	Slough Borough Council	~1,700	<u>Upton Court Park</u> (case study)
Validated	MacArthur Green	~10,000	<u>Lochgair</u> (on UK Land Carbon Registry)

Notable in this list is Slough Borough Council, which was one of the first LAs to use the Woodland carbon code and grow its own units. York County Council and Buckinghamshire CC have also followed their example. (Forestry Commission 2021)

In order for woodland to be considered as offsets, they need to cross the hurdle of additionality. How and why is Slough Borough Council able to count the new woodland as an additional project? It comes down to the fact that the council is not required to create new woodland and therefore if it decides to do so, it is additional to its legal duties. The fact that the new carbon sink has been created without any real need for it means that it is additional.

The question then arises as to the potential value for woodlands or parks or similar sinks (new as well as already existing) as carbon offsets within the land of local authorities around the country. Are Local Authorities legally required to maintain woodland and other sinks, if not, would they qualify as carbon offsets? Two questions to ask

1. What is legally required?
2. What is additional to legal duty?

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Green Assets as Additional Assets

Legal Responsibilities of Local Authorities

In considering the viability of green assets as ‘Additional’ we have considered the green portfolio of a local authority in Hertfordshire, that is East Herts District Council (“EHDC”).

Green Asset	Legal Duty	Additionality Consideration
Managed Trees	Health & safety obligations; Tree Preservation Orders (TPOs) discretionary	Tree maintenance beyond safety requirements is additional
Ancient Woodlands	Protected under National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF)	Conservation initiatives beyond planning law are additional
Soil	Duty to address contaminated land	Proactive soil carbon management is additional
Wetlands	Legally protected (Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981)	Not additional
Grass Verges & Football Pitches	No legal obligation	Entirely additional

Managed trees:

The ownership of a tree is determined by the owner of the land upon which the tree grows, and EHDC owns trees across a range of sites throughout the District but principally within its Parks and Open Spaces and Housing Sites. Under both Common Law and Statute, the owner of the land on which a tree stands has responsibilities for the health and safety of those on or near the land and has potential liabilities arising from the falling of a tree (or part of a tree). (Occupiers' Liability Acts 1957 & 1984) The standard of care is that of a reasonable and prudent landowner. Employers have a duty to ensure, so far as is reasonably practicable, that employees and members of the public are not put at risk in the course of their undertaking (Health & Safety at Work Act 1974).

All the trees in EHDC's ownership or responsibility are surveyed on a rolling three-year inspection cycle as part of its best practices. As part of tree management, many councils have adhered to best practices like British Standard BS 3998:2010 (Tree Work – Recommendations).

Under Environmental Protection Act 1990, councils are responsible for inspecting parks and gardens for land contamination and environmental hazards: this indirectly constitutes tree monitoring.

Under the amended Environmental Protection Act 1990, LAs have a duty of biodiversity under **Section 28G**: This imposes a duty on local authorities to take steps to conserve biodiversity in Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSIs) and manage green spaces with high ecological value.

Section 198 of the Town and Country Planning Act 1990 gives local planning authorities (i.e., councils) the power to make tree preservation orders **TPOs**. These orders protect specific trees or woodlands by prohibiting their cutting down, uprooting, topping, lopping, wilful damage, or destruction without the council's consent. **All the trees protected by tree conservation orders fall under the responsibility of the council too.**

Local authorities can make TPOs **under Section 198** to protect specific trees and woodlands, particularly when they are under threat from development. It is a criminal offence to damage or remove trees under a TPO without permission.

Under Paragraph 170 of **National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF)**, councils must contribute to and enhance the natural environment by protecting and improving biodiversity, ensuring that new developments include provisions for green spaces. Paragraph 171: Encourages councils to plan positively for biodiversity, using tools like Green Infrastructure Strategies.

Section 2 of **The Local Government Act 2000** provides councils with a broad power to do anything they consider likely to achieve the promotion of the environmental well-being of their areas. This includes protecting green spaces, promoting biodiversity, and supporting climate resilience.

Managed Trees: Conclusion

1. What is legally required?

Health and safety requirements in relation to Managed trees. TPOs are discretionary. There is a broad duty to promote biodiversity.

2. What is additional to legal duty?

Managed trees on council land are additional to legal duty, there is no legal duty to keep trees on council land.

Ancient Woodlands:

Paragraph 180 of **National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF)** provides strong protections for ancient woodlands, requiring councils to refuse planning applications that cause harm to these areas except in wholly exceptional circumstances.

The Forestry Act 1967 requires local authorities to seek approval from the Forestry Commission for significant felling activities, ensuring that woodland management and conservation are regulated.

The Countryside and Right of way Act 2000 in its **Section 85** requires councils to have regard to conserving and enhancing the natural beauty of the countryside when exercising their functions,

including urban parks, woodlands, and other green spaces. **Section 106** of Town and Country Planning Act, 1990 allows councils to enter into planning obligations with developers to secure contributions to green infrastructure and biodiversity as part of new developments.

Ancient Woodlands: Conclusion

1. What is legally required?

Ancient woodlands are not protected under the law.

2. What is additional to legal duty?

Preservation of ancient woodland on local authority land

Soil Protection:

The Environmental Protection Act 1990: Part IIA: Places a duty on councils to address contaminated land. Local authorities must ensure that land, including soil, is not harmful to human health or the environment.

Agriculture Act 2020: Focuses on sustainable farming and soil health, encouraging councils to support practices that protect soil quality, reduce erosion, and improve water retention through land management policies.

Soil Protection: Conclusion

1. What is legally required?

There is a legal duty to decontaminate contaminated land.

2. What is additional to legal duty?

Local authorities that maintain soil free of contamination, with sequestration capacity is not a legal duty of Local Authorities. Therefore, any such soil is additional to legal duty.

Protection of Wetlands:

Wildlife and Countryside Act 1981: Section 28: Protects Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSIs), many of which are wetlands. Councils must ensure that these areas are preserved and managed in line with conservation objectives.

Flood and Water Management Act 2010: Requires councils to manage surface water runoff and mitigate flood risks, which includes protecting natural wetlands that act as flood defences.

Protection of Wetlands: Conclusion

1. What is legally required?

Wetlands are protected by law, and impose a legal duty on any landowner, including local Authorities.

2. What is additional to legal duty?

Protection of wetlands is not additional to legal duty.

Football Pitches/Grass Verges:

National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF): Paragraph 174: Encourages councils to plan for the creation and protection of green infrastructure, including grassy verges and open green spaces, which contribute to biodiversity and ecosystem services

The Local Government Act 2000: Section 2: Grants councils the authority to promote environmental well-being, which can include protecting and enhancing urban green spaces and grassy verges for the health and enjoyment of the community.

Football Pitches/Grass Verges: Conclusion

1. What is legally required?

Grass verges are discretionary and not required legally.

2. What is additional to legal duty?

Grass verges and football pitches as carbon sinks are additional to legal duty.

New Developments in the Law: Protection of biodiversity and the ecosystem

The Environment Act of 2021 is the leading new law on the protection of biodiversity in the UK. It aims to set clear statutory targets for the recovery of the natural world in four priority areas: air quality, biodiversity, water and waste. It also introduces a new framework for biodiversity net gain,

requiring councils to ensure that developments lead to an overall increase in biodiversity. This means that green assets like trees and woodlands must be replaced and enhanced when affected by new developments. In terms of a legal duty for Local Authorities, a broad duty to protect and enhance biodiversity exists under the new Environment Act. The ‘biodiversity duty’ refers to a legal obligation placed on all public authorities in England to actively consider and implement measures to conserve and enhance biodiversity within their operations, essentially requiring them to take steps to protect and increase the variety of living species in their area.

The 2021 Environment Act as a risk to Legal Additionality of Green Assets

As the ‘biodiversity duty’ is overarching, potentially all green assets could be covered by this duty leaving open the possibility of nullifying the legal additionality of green assets.

But a cursory analysis of the scope of the biodiversity duty throws doubt on the power of this duty to nullify additionality in green assets. Under the biodiversity duty, there is no specificity as to the type of biodiversity to be protected. At any given point in time, a duty holder such as a local authority could choose to protect an element of biodiversity, such as a woodland, for example. It makes no difference to the execution of the duty if it were to have been a different element of biodiversity to be protected, such as a grassland, for example. Therefore, while there is a broad duty to protect biodiversity, there is also no specific duty towards a particular element of biodiversity. It is arguable that the biodiversity duty will not have an impact on legal additionality of green assets. As there is a choice in the type of biodiversity that can be protected, any biodiversity protected under the 2021 legislation may be considered additional to legal duty.

A suggested approach is to explore a cut-off date for legal additionality. Any duties enshrined in laws passed before that cut-off date would nullify legal additionality of the green asset. Any duties that arise from laws after the cut-off date will not affect the legal additionality of green assets. By this token, if 2008 were to be taken as a cut-off date for legal additionality in the UK, the 2021 Environment Act’s biodiversity duty does not count when determining legal additionality of green assets. It would also not count if the cut-off date was brought further forward, to 2019. The reasons for citing 2008 and 2019 as cut-off days are because of the UK climate change law and regulation in 2008 and 2019 respectively. The UK committed itself to a target of net zero by 2050 through the 2019 regulation.

Further research is needed into the Biodiversity duty vis a vis additionality.

Offsetting in a LA Context

Local Authorities have a dual responsibility in relation to emissions reductions, that of reducing their own operational emissions, and taking charge of the territorial emissions. Currently, neither of these are legal responsibilities. This poses several challenges, including issues such as keeping to the political promise flowing from declarations of climate emergencies and considering the potential to claim carbon credit for administering central government grants for decarbonisation schemes.

Most LAs are currently focused on their own operational emissions. Local Authorities should be differentiated from commercial entities. Commercial entities have in their business plans to produce products or provide services which lead to emissions. From a sectoral point of view, LAs are not an IPCC 'sector' (IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change). Given their very small proportion of contribution to GHG emissions, the role of LAs to influence actors is of greater value than their role in getting their house in order. Local implementation of mitigation is key to achieving GHG emissions reductions. There are no such thing as national emissions, there are only territorial emissions covering the geography of the nation, i.e. UK territorial emissions are the sum total of UK LA geographical emissions.

It is with the realm of possibility that Local Authorities are already net zero in their emissions, if their green assets are counted as carbon sinks, and counted into their baselining of emissions. Therefore, the subject matter of this report, and the findings could provide new direction to climate action of Local Authorities.

This report has considered green assets for their potential as high-quality offsets. Green assets enable carbon removals from the atmosphere. Carbon reduction projects such as better heating solutions also count as carbon offsets. Taken as a whole, there are further avenues of research to consider regarding how to accurately and efficiently measure the carbon value of these green assets, as well as considering how other non-statutory local authority activities (outside of green assets) may sequester or avoid LA carbon emissions or those of its residents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Green assets such as parks, woodlands, trees, soil, and grass verges act as carbon sinks making their protection necessary, and their expansion desirable. However, the principle of additionality has historically limited their consideration as carbon offsets. This report finds that additionality applies to private sector actors with limited duties towards emissions reduction, i.e. confined to their own operational emissions.

In contrast, public sector emissions reductions – such as those progressed under climate emergency response activity – warrant a different approach. This research recommends that the principle of additionality be understood as stratified into different degrees when applying additionality to public sector voluntary emissions reductions. The concept of additionality must recognise that LAs already maintain green assets without a legal obligation to do so. The recommendation suggests a stratified additionality framework classifying offsets based on the degree of additionality and through the corresponding integrity of sequestration.

This approach will:

- Enable greater transparency in how the offset value of green assets is communicated to the public
- Highlight differentiated responsibilities of different climate actors
- Clarify a communication plan for carbon offset strategies to address green washing concerns

- Help LAs assess the value of green assets in their areas
- Support climate finance opportunities for new green asset development for local authorities in the future.

In sum, the recommendations of this report are -

- 1. Stratify additionality**
 - a. Establish different degrees of additionality tailored to the public sector**
 - b. Differentiate the value of offsets based on asset types and management practices**
- 2. Quantify and certify Green Asset Offsets**
 - a. Review and agree upon the carbon sequestration potential capacity of managed trees, woodlands, soil, grass verges and pitches.**
 - b. Align standards with recognised certification schemes**
- 3. Develop a clear carbon offset strategy**
 - a. Define principles appropriate for the public sector**
 - b. Enhance transparency to avoid greenwashing concerns.**
- 4. Consider the climate finance potential of increasing green assets**
 - a. Explore funding mechanisms to increase green asset portfolio**

Given that legal duties surrounding green assets are evolving, this report emphasizes the importance of staying updated on local government law and practice. The Biodiversity Act 2021 and the legal duty towards biodiversity under the 2021 Biodiversity Act require further investigation, to understand how legal requirements interact with additionality assessments. Finally, establishing a clear cut-off date for additionality will help to formalise additional or discretionary green asset management from statutory LA obligations.

Conclusion

The Paris Agreement has broadened emissions reductions duties, enlisting more economies in climate action. Whilst beneficial, this has also resulted in rigid carbon market principles that may not fully align with the role of the public sector.

This research has critically examined the concept of additionality, discovering inconsistencies in practical understanding and application, particularly for local authorities. By assessing whether LAs have legal duties toward carbon sinks - collectively referred to in this report as green assets – it was determined that, barring wetlands, other green assets assessed, such as managed trees, ancient woodlands, soil, grass verges exist at the discretion of their landowners, i.e. local authorities. Given this, LAs can derive benefit by counting these into carbon offset strategies, ensuring they are recognised as legitimate, high-quality carbon offsets for residual emissions.

By embracing a stratified additionality framework, LAs can enhance transparency, leverage the benefit of their green assets and contribute to net zero goals. By establishing clear principles, securing financial mechanisms and improving verification and accounting standards, LAs will be able to focus their efforts on wider community emissions while fulfilling their obligations to climate mitigation, biodiversity and adaptation.

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